

PRIMARY EDUCATION AS AN EXAMPLE OF TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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In the students agility and promptness

physical adjectives development technology "

Abstract.

This in the article state education standards and study program based on initial education physical education science education of children health save , their physically mature being their achievements for conditions Create about word is conducted

Key words.

state education standards , mobile games , standard , gymnastics exercises

INTRODUCTION

General medium of education all sciences such as physical education Science is also a state education standards and study program based on is taught . Study program study process done increase main from the documents is considered Educational science program physical education education content , its students by of mastering the most efficient methods , information sources and standards shown normative documents is considered Physical education from science Created this study program in practice applied came to programs critical approached , their the most good aspects , advanced school of teachers and another of specialists positive the work experiences attention received without again work developed _ At school 2 hours per week held physical education lesson to the child's organism complete physical upload to give for enough that it is not and scientific to research according to of students diary to action has been physiological 45 minutes physical education lesson only 11 % account received without Uzbekistan Republic People education ministry 1-4 grade students with addition training lessons transfer for school available from the clock to use , up to 3 hours a week , if where chance if so , 4-5 hours physical education hours to pass permission done _

MAIN PART

In our country to football has been attention as a result common medium education

physical education to the program football for separately hour to be separated recommendation given _ Football game methods and technical elements in teaching children with training organize to do forms big important have _ First students at the stage (4th grade). with of work main method group being to teach directed . Football according to study in their classes applied all exercises conditional respectively three to the group to be possible : special preparation , general preparation , competition . His using young people each completion physical development duties successful solution reach can _

Teacher in grades 1-4 physical education in their classes so pedagogical task that 's it task mobile games , gymnastics exercises and light athletics complex apply based on solution will be done . Active games separately important have they are _ in students main movement qualifications forms , grows is coming young generation to form positive effect shows . Active in their games efficient use and them organize to do for enough in quantity manuals to be necessary _ Of these come came out without , teachers in front the following tasks to put to the goal is compatible with :

- mobile games and of them use methodology circle their own knowledge degrees increase _

- students with mobile games transfer and organize to do for at school necessary the conditions to create reach _

- to children mobile to the games interest wake up and them independent respectively organize to do to teach

" Swimming " section to the program included being , this in the department separately hour not allocated , however at school to swim conditions if so , to him the first from class starting from

is taught . Hour and , of the program main types (movable games , gymnastics , light

at the expense of athletics , sports games) . take will go Training per week two times

will be held . Swimming to class going in students soap , mop , towel , swimming for special to have clothes (plavka , kupalnik) . need _ Lesson in the process security to the rules strictly compliance reach Demand will be done .

Study 1-4 grades to the program for national dance elements included . to this section each in class to the circumstances looking known time separation to the goal is appropriate . For example : for grades 1-4 below dance elements included : "

Wohay Bola", " Chittigul ", " Andijan polka ", " Lazgi ", " Gulnoz ", " Shuh girls ", " Askariy ", " Hawthorn " and others _ of the program this department transfer for teacher , of course preparation to see must music to the cassette written to be from girls assistant (soloist) selection training during students on time encouraged , right assessment necessary _

1st Class. Students alone - alone one by one , in pairs from two being short to distances walking and run sure to perform to teach Short ropes , ropes to jump tall didn't happen from the barriers to the " pit". to jump sure target to throw to teach Various from obstacles gymnastics from the seat and also to the walls scratching out and over to pass to teach Walking-running jump and to throw exercises embodied mobile in the games participation to achieve In the water self catch to know to teach National dance actions to teach and to dance fall _ In the morning simple gymnastics exercises independent do it to get to teach

2nd Class. 20-30 meters to the distance right from the corridor from each other out past fast to run ; slowly and one 100-150-200 meters at a pace to the distance walking and to run ; the ball long and sure to the distance to throw ; 30 on the rope until to jump from the place

running come to the length jumps ; 25 meters to the distance to swim ; Andijan _ to the music of " polka ", " Lazgi ", " Yalla". dance to fall ; the team in the account mobile in the games to participate to know necessary _ Independent respectively morning hygienic gymnastics exercises do it to know to teach it is necessary

3rd Class. The following do it to receive to know need _ 30-40 meters run slowly _ to run in moderation 200 distance at speed in sections (100-200 meters walking and running) 2-3 times perform , jump the pit from the edge running to arrive deysinib to the length jump _ jumping from a hill (50-60 cm). falls , the ball away and sure target from the place standing up to throw 60-80 times on the twine jump _ mobile in the games class with participation , game rules basis to know free in case of 25-50 meters in the water speaking transition _ national of dances main actions to know Gulnoz , Shuh _ girl ", " Lazgi ", " Yalla ", " Kari navo ", " Pakhtaoy " and hakoza _ In the morning hygienic gymnastics perform _

4th Class. Physical education in their classes self protection to do the rules to know therefore the following perform it is necessary That's right from the corridor nimble run , group with together with 60 meters to the distance to run slowly running 200 meters 3-4 times the distance (with rest) is moderate at speed to run to the length and to the height running come to jump the ball long to the distance sure 3-4 steps to the target leave to throw shuttlecock on the run given the assignment to perform the ball hanging take to throw the ball with to move football and sports

games elements simplified elements replace to perform mobile the games the team in the presence of mother the head or captain as to perform morning complex gymnastics to perform

CONCLUSION

Physical education lessons from transfer the goal is children health save , their physically mature being their achievements for conditions Create and in training safety to the rules compliance to do skills shaping _

How in case be it all of possibilities using , physical education

lessons regularly organize reach , in them of students active participation provide to the organism useful downloads to give very important _

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